

An Evaluation of the Implementation of the Model of Integrated Care for Type 2 Diabetes in two Community Health Organizations

INTEGRATED CARE TEAM TOPIC GUIDE

- Thank participant, introduce researcher & study
- Outline information sheet, consent form, highlight permission to record interview
- Remind and emphasise that it is a study to understand the acceptability and feasibility of the integrated care service i.e., we want to know how to improve the service, how it works in real life practice – please be honest

Topic	Prompt/probe directly prompt
<p><u>Introduction</u></p> <p>Tell me about your role, what is involved?</p> <p>How does the service compare with what was done (in this area) before it was introduced?</p> <p>Do you feel the integrated diabetes care service is valuable/worthwhile? Why?</p>	<p>What parts are extra? What parts were done already?</p>
<p><u>Delivering the service</u></p> <p>Thinking about the integrated care service overall; what works well /less well?</p> <p>Tell me about XX... How do you find that? How does that work?</p> <p>...collecting the service activity data.</p> <p>...referrals to other services.</p> <p>...delivering education sessions (HCPs, patients)</p> <p>...patient appointments (F2F or virtual)</p>	<p>What helps service delivery? What would make it easier to deliver? Were there any parts of your role you cannot do/parts of your service you cannot deliver? Would you change anything about the service?</p> <p>Are there any logistical issues?</p> <p>Are there any issues? If so, what?</p> <p>When did you do this? (i.e., between patients, during consultations, after hours)</p> <p>Prompt, as appropriate for HCP being interviewed: referrals <i>to</i> dietician (hospital/community), CNS, podiatrist, diabetes OPD (via GP), referrals <i>from</i> residential care facility, homebound patients.</p> <p>Which HCPs attended? Any differences by group? Prompt: GPs, PNs, PHNs, residential care home staff, other HCPs</p>

<u>Patient perspective</u> Have you had any feedback from patients?	Positive or negative?
<u>To finish</u> Is the service sustainable? Anything else you want to mention about your experience of delivering the service?	Why/Why not?